

on the whole very well preserved, but there are several clerical errors which I have corrected. The name of the thera Majima or Majiba occurs here and in No. 8, and also in an inscription at Piduruwagala wihāra near Sigiri (No. 43), but cannot be identified. A village, Patanangala, exists at present about 38 miles from Hambantota in the southern province, and it is also mentioned on the large slab from Tissamahārāma (No. 67), line 7, 8, 15, but I do not know whether it is the identical one.

8. Periyakadu wihāra. This is a rock temple, four miles to the north of Dehelgomuwa, a village eight miles from Kurunaegala, on the Dambulla road. The inscription is on a flat rock about 100 yards from the temple, generally overgrown with jungle; it is very well preserved, only in the 2nd and 3rd line two or three letters are missing. The Cakkadhāraka wihāra is mentioned here, and in an inscription at Wihāragala (No. 11), but not known from the Mahāvansa.

9. Andarawaewa, near Elagamuwa, on the central road, 11 miles from Dambulla; flat stone, formerly used as a pillar. About half a mile off are extensive ruins at Korasagala. The inscription is imperfect, and does not allow of a translation, but the name of King Wahaba (66.—110 A.D.) is clearly legible on the stone.

10. Galwana, a stone in the bed of the spillwater stream of Mekiccaewa, about 120 yards from the high road at the 16th mile of the Anurādhapura-Trincomalee road. The inscription is tolerably well preserved, but the names of the two tanks contain clerical errors, so that they cannot be identified.

11. Wihāragala, 2½ miles west of Galenbinduru waewa, on the 20th mile of the eastern minor road, where it joins the Sipukulama road. Two inscriptions, the first bears the name of King Wasaba, of which, curiously enough, the first syllable is omitted; the second that of Gajabāhu, with the usual genealogy. The tank mentioned in both inscriptions is the Uppala doniya tank, and there is also made allusion to the Pabbatārāmaya wihāra (Mah., p. 207).

12. Tāmaragala, about two miles from the 13th mile post, Anurādhapura-Trincomalee road, Uddiyankulam Korle. Inscription imperfect, containing the name of Gajabāhu, with the usual genealogy.

13. Kaikāwa wihāra, four miles from Balalla, close to the road to Yāpahoo (north-western province). The inscription is near a small tank on the left from the footpath leading to the wihāra, quite overgrown with jungle, but very well preserved. The king is only called Aba here, without the usual genealogy, but the form of the character points to the time of Gajabāhu. There is another inscription on the top of the rock beyond the wihāra, in the same character, but too much defaced to allow of a translation.

14. Patahagawagala, at Niyadawane wihāra, about 4 miles to the west of Polpiṭigāma, a village 26 miles from Kurunaegala, on the Anurādhapura road. The inscription is almost totally

gaṇaya Cakadarika wehe (5) rahi cetahaṭa ca bikusagahaṭa (6) dine Cakadaraka wehera [hi] dine.

(10.) Galwana.—Maharajaha Wahabaya pu (2) manumaraka Tisa maharajaha puta (3) maharaji Gamini Abayaṭa pala wibajakahi wana manaka wawi paca saha[sa] kahawana jaraya kaṇawaya tā baraba bukasagahaṭaya catari paceni pari

(11.) Wihāragala.—(a.) Siddham. [Wa] saba raja Cakadaraka wiharahi papa (2) takara kara waya upala donika wawi paca sahasa (3) kiniya paca satehi ya pasu nawaya bikusagahaṭaya (4) nawasa.

(b.) Siddham. Wahaba rajahi patagapara Tisa rajaha (2) puti Gamiṇi Aba raji [Wa] saba rajaha dinika Upala (3) donika wawi papatakara jina pahawaya para sagaha (4) ṭa padi dina.

(12.) Tāmaragala.—Siddha Wahaba ra ha marumanaka Tisa maharajaha puta maharaja Gamini Abaya

(13.) Kaikāwa wihāra.—Siddham. Patama tera Warasi ametaha jita Amaryawa ameti Abaha ca duti bati kara bu hawa karu ga waḍhacetaḥaṭa ja bikasagahaṭa ja dina.

(15.) Dunumaṇḍalakaṇḍa.—(b.) Ulajakawapi bikasagaha (2) sitaṭa wiyaketahi bujaha (3) bika anutara be bājana hala (4) ṭa kubara duṇa kariha ṇa gamaka (5) ketahi sagakubari aṭa karihaka (6) tulatarawiyaketahi tanakare (7) waye bukasagahaṭa kubare dinaka (8) rahi ka[ha] pana ha gainakarahi wirawa (9) Abaya bukasagahaṭa kubara dina sata (10) masaka.

(16.) Situlpawihāra. — Siddham. Nakamaharajaha puta Batiya Tisa maharajaha maḷu Ti[sa] (2) maharaja aṭasa ta Tisa kahawana ṭabiya Citalapawata atiṇa samaya dakini Ti (3) sa aleya wawi akaḷa koṭu kaṇa waya Nakamaharajaha [ce] taha ta Muḷawatiyaṭa ci (4) hata karadorahi tumaha akaḷa [ko] ṭu karitakojarahalayaṭa ca dasa pahataṭaya (5) jina [paḷi] satari koṭu dini dakapata sakalagamata dini.

(17.) Galgirikaṇḍa.—Sidha Batiya rajaha dinayanikaka gala-kawiharahi kubara pahana wi (2) maduka kubara ceta ma waruta hinagala awapataya nakawiraya ceta-kubara asirawu tabu (3) ketahi cetakara mani karawiya ceta kubara gaṇawi kaṭiyaya cetakubara.

(18.) Demaṭamal wihāra.—Siddham. Gāmaka Aba rajaha wihare sataha gamaka (2) Sariṭuri ha giriya boja pati pati daka parihaka gapa (3) wiharahi dasa

(19.) Debelgalpansala.— Mekawana Aba maharaja (2) catali ta haṭa maka Aba (3) calawada puninasaha maha bahudawasa ga (4) naka sawasayaha jata tabana lawā (5) mahawiharahi papatakarahiya kaṇa saga waḍawa (6) tara mahapata wana mahapataka mahamataṭa (7) tasa jinahaṭa sapa

(20.) Mihintale.—Sidha. Dewānapiya maharājaha marumanaka manapaya Gāmini Abhaya maharajaha Cetigiriya bhikhusagaha (2) gara gāmanakārīkahi pule-

himself Majjhima having made six (?) together with a water strainer he gave it.

(8.) Periyakaḍu wihāra:—From King Gāmini Abhaya [an order]: In the year Puwadara Sawanaka the four great tanks of the chief thera Tusa and the four gaṇas of the chief thera Majjhima are given to the caitya in the Cakkadhāraka wihāra and to the congregation of the priests. To the Cakkadhāraka wihāra they are given.

(10.) Galwana:—To the grandson of the great king Wasabha, the son of the great king Tissa. The great king Gāmini Abhaya he distributed a tank 5,000 karshāpaṇas (in circumference) having dug it out [he gave] to the priesthood the four pratyayas.

(11.) Wihāragala:—(a.) Hail! King Wasabha repaired the dilapidated buildings at the Cakkadhāraka wihāra and at the Uppala doṇiya tank; five thousand karīshas and five hundred [he gave] to the priesthood

(b.) Hail! [The grandson] of King Wasabha the son of King Tisa, King Gāmini Abhaya, repaired the Uppala doṇiya tank which was bestowed [on the temple] by King Wasabha, and gave it to the priesthood.

(13.) Kaikāwa wihāra:—Hail! Amaryawā, the daughter of the chief thera minister Warasi (?), and the second brother of the minister Abhaya, gave to the Waḍha caitya and to the priesthood.

(16.) Situlpawihāra:—Hail! The son of King [Mallaka] Nāga, the brother of King Batiya Tissa, King [Kaniṭṭha] Tissa repaired the Cittalapabbata established by Kākawaṇṇa Tissa and the tanks of Dakkhīna and Tissa and the caitya of King Nāga; having remitted the taxes and having performed deeds not (formerly) done (even) by himself having repaired the decayed buildings after having seen he gave it over altogether.

(18.) Demaṭamal wihāra:—Hail! King Gāmaka (mistake for Gāmini) Abhaya, having made inhabited the wihāra and a hundred villages and Saritūrigiri, having seen the Gapa-wihāra ten

(61.) Habarane:—Hail! On account of the inundated villages Abhaya, son of the minister Wasabha, saw the Agiwaḷamana tank and the elephant's tank; having built several villages near lakes without furnishing the fields with a tank between embankments for the flowing down (of the water), he constructed the Agiwaḷamana tank out of the Mula lake and the Pacawadi lake. His Majesty, the great king, after having made serve this Agiwaḷamana tank 1046 karīshas, having given it in charge to Abalaya, son of Sena, an aged overseer, to watch the embankment, and to his grandson Wesamana [to watch] the field, having seen the new (?) karīshas and the ammanas, having caused this to be written on a stone belonging to the priesthood, after assigning the Karakaḷa tank, and having performed deeds not (formerly)